

D4.1 ANNUAL REPORT ON TRAINING ACTIVITIES OF THE ACTION – MONTH 24

WP Leader: Prof. Raffaella Colombatti, University of Padua, Italy; Dr. Elisabetta Mezzalira, University of Padua, Italy.

WG4: Education, training, and capacity building

1. Description of Working Group and its role in the HELIOS network

The working group 4 (WG) focuses on developing education, training, and capacity-building tools to facilitate knowledge transfer among participants regarding the topic of haemoglobinopathies. WG4 promotes networking and training opportunities through laboratory exchanges, participation in training schools and workshops, and active research collaboration by sharing primary data and analytical protocols. It also fosters direct interaction between various stakeholders by creating a multidisciplinary forum. WG4 aligns with objectives CBO1 (To promote the participation of YRIs, women and researchers from ITCs in the network and in leadership roles of the Action), CBO3 (To develop a European training program for haemoglobinopathies), and CBO4 (To strengthen interaction and dialogue between cross-sectoral groups).

The group's tasks include developing a comprehensive training program with workshops and scientific meetings, implementing short-term scientific missions (STSMs) for training in specialist labs and establishing a mentoring program for young researchers. Initially, the group had as one of the objectives also the creation of a multidisciplinary forum for discussing haemoglobinopathies, with both online and regular in-person or virtual meetings every three months. However Given the ongoing webinars, frequent working group meetings, and feedback forms through which members communicate community needs, the Action decided to facilitate discussions through these existing channels instead.

2. Objectives & deliverables

Objectives of WP4	Deliverable no. (D)
4.1 To develop a comprehensive training programme, including workshops, training schools and participation in scientific meetings	D 4.1
4.2 To implement STSMs to extend training in specialist laboratories or clinics, aimed at providing extensive theoretical and practical knowledge.	D 4.1
4.3 To implement a mentoring programme for YRIs. Senior network members will be teamed with YRIs through regular discussions about diverse topics related to the disease and career development.	D 4.1
4.4 To create a multidisciplinary forum for discussing topics related to haemoglobinopathies, including stakeholders from all areas of haemoglobinopathies. Not implemented	D 4.2

M. info@heliosaction.eu

W. www.heliosaction.eu

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Deliverable no.	Description	Month
D 4.1	Annual reports on training activities of the Action (four in total)	12
		24
		36
		48
D 4.2	Report on the formation, membership, and discussion points of the multidisciplinary forum for haemoglobinopathies (initial release & update)	48

3. Description of the work done during the first grant period with a reference to the deliverable timeline (training school, grants granted, monthly discussion club, invited speaker series, survey)

➤ Continuous management of the Young Research Investigators (YRIs) Monthly discussion club:

The monthly discussion club has been managed and advertised among the members of the action. It is a scientific online meeting specifically targeting the educational development needs of YRIs. YRIs have the chance to present the current status and results of scientific work on haemoglobinopathies to the network. Moreover, it includes lectures given by the researchers who have been granted the funds for a short-term scientific mission (STSM). These researchers can share with the network their experience, challenges and achievements of the STSM, along with the learning outcomes of the experience. It is regularly held once a month, in an online format, to enable wide participation.

➤ Invited Speaker Series (Monthly recurrence):

The invited speaker series features monthly talks delivered by invited speakers. The speakers are selected based on their wide expertise on their field, as regards haemoglobinopathies, and on the basis of the selection of recently published articles that might be of interest to the action members on novel and intriguing findings on hemoglobinopathies are invited to present their work to the HELIOS network. The lectures are delivered online, on a monthly basis.

➤ Organization of the second in-person training school:

The training School was held as an in-person 3-days event in Nicosia, Cyprus, in the dates 12-14 of May, on the topic of FAIR Principles Training School, designed to help researchers apply Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) principles to their data. Action members from many different parts of the world joined the event as trainers, sharing with the trainees' practical guidance on integrating FAIR principles into real-world research on rare diseases. The training school provided invaluable insights

into data management, essential for the trainees that are approaching and deepening their understanding of research on rare diseases.

- Grant awards for Short Term Scientific Missions (STSM) And Participation To Conferences
A total of 8 STSM and and 6 Conference grants were awarded in the second year of HELIOS Cost Action

List Of Topics Of the grantees during their The Short Term Scientific Missions (STSM) And Participation To Conferences

Name	Country	Topic STSM
Tamana Stella	Cyprus	Capacity Building in FAIRification Processes for Haemoglobinopathy Registries and Research Use Cases
Burak DURMAZ	Türkiye	Leveraging MRD Detection Methods for Comprehensive Hematologic Disease Monitoring: From Leukemia to Hemoglobinopathies
Coralea Stephano u	Cyprus	Artificial Intelligence and Ethics in Biomedical Research, with a Focus on Rare Diseases
Leonid Bystrykh	Netherlands	Stratification of Thalassemia intermedia and major patients through integration of omics data
Norafiza Mohd Yasin	Netherlands	Enhancing Thalassaemia Diagnostic Capacity Through DEVYSER-Based Genotyping
Alessandro Cellini	Italy	The building of a transition program for patients with Sickle Cell Disease, other hemoglobinopathies or rare anaemias—perspective training for the adult haematologist
Giulia Reggiani	Italy	Towards a shared transition program for patients with Sickle Cell Disease
Maria Badikyan	Armenia	Advancing Expertise in Benign Hematology: Clinical and Laboratory Training at Department of Clinical and Community Sciences, University of Milan

Name	Country	Conference Type	Topic
Jelena Roganovic	Croatia	Inclusiveness Target	Thalassemia syndromes in

			Countries Conference	children: Croatian experience
Liri Seraj	Albania		Young Researcher and Innovator Conference	Projected Impact of Thalidomide on Transfusion Burden in a Cohort of Thalassemia Major Patients: A Data-Driven Analysis
Antri Florentia Romanou	Cyprus		Young Researcher and Innovator Conference	Long-read-amplicon haplotyping for β -thalassaemia preimplantation genetic testing for couples with no additional family members
Stefania Byrou	Cyprus		Young Researcher and Innovator Conference	Non-Invasive Determination of the Paternal Inheritance in Pregnancies at Risk for β -Thalassaemia by Analyzing Cell-Free Fetal DNA Using Targeted Next-Generation Sequencing
Elisabetta Mezzalira	Italy		Young Researcher and Innovator Conference	Identifying, categorising, and mapping stakeholders involved in the delivery of care in haematological rare diseases: process analysis, a multi-method protocol
Elona Hasalla	Albania		Young Researcher and	Distribution of Hemoglobinopathies in the Elbasan

M. info@heliosaction.eu

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Innovator
Conference

Region and the
Importance of their
early diagnosis
treatment

➤ Dissemination and manuscript drafting of “HELIOS WG4 Survey: Education, training, and capacity building”. Manuscript currently under revision:

Effective management of hemoglobinopathies requires specialized knowledge and collaboration among healthcare professionals (HCPs). With an increasing number of patients needing specialized care across Europe, there is an urgent need to train the next generation of HCPs to improve patient outcomes and quality of life. This study aimed to map the expertise and educational priorities of trainees and mentors involved in hemoglobinopathy care and research within the European COST Action HELIOS.

Methods: A cross-sectional online survey covering multidisciplinary aspects of hemoglobinopathy diagnosis, management, and treatment was co-designed by researchers coming from different backgrounds (nursing, biology, internal medicine and pediatrics). The survey codesign was preceded by a targeted literature review that identified key topics, which were refined through final expert consensus involving professionals from multiple countries. The survey assessed availability and area of expertise of potential mentors, possible training activities, alongside trainees' educational priorities. It was then conducted among HELIOS participants from September 2024 to January 2025. Responses were analyzed using descriptive statistics and comparative analyses to assess variations in training needs across regions, age groups, and professional roles.

Results: A total of 76 HELIOS participants from 27 countries responded in the initial release of the survey. Most respondents were aged 30–49 (78%) and held PhDs (78.3%), primarily working in teaching hospitals (52%) or research institutes (30.7%). Physicians were the largest group (39.5%), with 13 other professional roles represented. A majority (66%) were interested in receiving training, including 18 mentors who also sought to advance their knowledge in specific areas such as multidisciplinary management, psychosocial care, and palliative care. Mentor expertise focused on molecular pathophysiology (50%) and diagnosis (43.3%), with gaps in implementation science, ethics, pain management, and patient monitoring (all ~20%). Underrepresented areas included hematopoietic cell transplantation, palliative care, and interprofessional models (all ≤14%). Trainees prioritized diagnosis (86%), research (84%), ethics (80%), and emerging areas such as AI (91%), although rated all survey topics as important, expressing at least 44% interest for each topic. No significant regional or age differences were observed.

Conclusion: The survey reveals expertise in molecular pathophysiology and evidence-based screening and diagnosis, but highlights gaps in comprehensive patient management, palliative care, and psychosocial aspects. These gaps align with high trainee demand, reflecting the growing complexity of hemoglobinopathy management.

Remarkably, trainees expressed significant interest across all surveyed topics, with each garnering at least 40% interest. This broad enthusiasm, coupled with mentors' interest in receiving additional training in specific areas, underscores the current lack of a well-rounded and systematic educational approach. To address these needs effectively, adopting a participatory needs assessment approach in selecting topics and implementing diverse educational strategies (e.g., hands-on workshops, mentorship programs, journal clubs) is a key aspect to ensure the creation of both rigorous and relevant training. Such a program will be designed by HELIOS to keep pace with the changing landscape of hemoglobinopathy care, to equip emerging specialists with the diverse skill set required for delivering comprehensive, patient-focused care.

- Dissemination and manuscript drafting of “Evaluating Artificial Intelligence Literacy and Perceptions among Hematology Healthcare Professionals”. Manuscript currently in preparation.

Preliminary evidence of Artificial Intelligence (AI) introduction in healthcare shows strong potential in enhancing patient outcomes. In hematology, applications are emerging rapidly. To support successful AI integration into health care systems, it is crucial to assess healthcare professionals' (HCPs) understanding of basic AI concepts, as well as their attitudes and expectations regarding its clinical application. It was administered a cross-sectional validated survey which covered demographics, work setting, AI-related knowledge, research involvement, perceived impact, implementation barriers, concerns, and clinical phases where AI could offer value. It targeted all healthcare professionals and researchers part of the European hematology community via ERN-EuroBloodNet and HELIOS, and was distributed through the EU Survey Platform between January and June 2025. Participation required electronic informed consent and complied with GDPR regulations.

Preliminary analysis included 73 participants from 25 countries across four continents: Europe (79.5%), Asia (11%), Africa (8.2%), and America (1.4%). Most worked in teaching hospitals (74%). Of the sample, 64.4% were involved in clinical practice and research, while 35.6% were exclusively researchers. Physicians comprised 49.3%—predominantly senior attendings (69.4%)—with the rest being nurses, biologists, and other HCPs. Educationally, 24.3% had an MSc and 56.8% held a PhD.

Regarding AI knowledge, 74% correctly pointed to the definition of “Machine Learning (ML),” though 38.4% were unsure, and 22.5% of those confident answered incorrectly. For “Deep Learning (DL),” 57.5% chose correctly, yet 47.9% were unsure, and 37% of confident respondents answered incorrectly. While 56.2% were familiar with “Big Data,” only 31.5% identified their core characteristics (Volume, Variety, Velocity).

AI tool usage was reported by 71.2%: 28.8% used one, 30.1% used two to four, and 12.3% used more than four. Tools included ChatGPT-like applications for data handling, natural language processing, and predictive models for diagnosis, prognosis, and patient safety. Big Data sources cited were wearable devices, genomics, multi-omics, and electronic health records.

A substantial 76.7% had read at least one AI-related hematology publication, and 37% were actively involved in AI projects. The perceived impact of AI was highly positive: 94.6%

believed it would improve both patient outcomes and their field. However, key implementation barriers included lack of skills/knowledge, limited funding, and restricted data access. Main concerns were privacy (61.6%), bias and fairness (60.3%), and accountability. While there is strong enthusiasm for AI in hematology, notable gaps in foundational knowledge exist. Many healthcare professionals struggle with correctly defining key AI terms, sometimes overestimating their understanding. As AI tools become increasingly embedded in clinical practice, their successful implementation will require focused training to prevent misuse and minimize bias. This transition may be challenging for both professionals and patients, highlighting the need for a structured and gradual approach. Supporting healthcare professionals through tailored educational opportunities will enhance critical thinking and decision-making capacity, easing the shift and reducing risks associated with rushed or incorrect implementation. A deliberate, inclusive strategy is essential to ensure that AI integration makes a meaningful and sustainable impact during this pivotal period of technological transformation.

➤ Development of targeted multidisciplinary training program

The HELIOS training program aims to address the educational needs of healthcare professionals, researchers, and data scientists in the field of hemoglobinopathies. It encompasses a diverse range of formats, including workshops, webinars, online self-learning modules, and case-based teaching. The program will cover topics such as patient-centered care, data analysis and AI, scientific writing, clinical research, ethics and social dimensions, and emerging treatments. The content is informed by survey results that identify areas of interest like molecular mechanisms, data analysis, ethical and legal issues, patient registries, and diagnosis in low-resource settings. The training program provides a comprehensive educational experience tailored to the HELIOS community and will be kicked off in Year 3 of HELIOS.

➤ Development of targeted mentorship program

Stemming from the participatory approach of the two surveys, the HELIOS Mentorship Program will offer a unique opportunity for professional growth and development within the HELIOS community. Running the 3rd year of HELIOS, the program will pair mentees with experienced mentors to foster collaboration, research development, professional growth, and leadership skills. Throughout the program, mentors and mentees will meet regularly, at least bi-monthly, to explore research opportunities, engage with the HELIOS community, and potentially undertake research stays or collaborations. The mentorship program will encourage hands-on experience, international collaboration, and the development of competencies aligned with the mentee's aspirations.

4. Future Activities

WG4 will continue to lead, organize and conduct the training activities above described.